

**YAPISAL SAĞLIĞI İZLEMENİN ÖNEMİ VE KÖPRÜLERE OLAN FAYDALARI:
LORAWAN KULLANMA İMKANI**

**THE IMPORTANCE OF STRUCTURAL HEALTH MONITORING AND ITS
BENEFITS FOR BRIDGES: POSSIBILITY OF USING LORAWAN**

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ABSTRACT

Over the past years, structural health monitoring systems (SHMs) have been used to track and assess the structural health of various structures such as tall buildings and skyscrapers, dams, tunnels, aerospace and the mostly important structure which is bridges. Given the vital role bridges play in transportation, SHM is frequently used for bridges. It is capable of identifying problems including foundation settling, corrosion, and fatigue. Nowadays, most structures are designed and built with a SHMs as a standard mechatronic system. New bridges are built every year, and in some countries the maintenance of these bridges is often neglected. Modern wireless sensor technologies are helping to develop automatic bridge safety monitoring systems. Sensors can be used to collect a variety of information such as vibration, water level and fire data. These data will be useful in assessing the structural health status of bridges. The main scope of the paper is to develop an integrated monitoring system for durability assessment of bridges and also trying to benefit from using LoRaWAN IoT technology. At the first section of the paper we will be discussing about how important the structural health monitoring (SHM) is and its utilities in general and on bridges fields. Afterwards we will briefly discuss about LoRaWAN Iot technology and how we can configure it and make it possible to be used to make the information handover more easier and safer.

Key Words: Structural Health Monitoring, SHM, IoT, Wireless Sensor Network, LoRaWAN, Internet of Things.

1. INTRODUCTION

Bridges, buildings, and dams are examples of infrastructure that are essential to our everyday existence because they keep us safe and make it easier for us to travel and conduct business. However, over time, many things might cause these structures to fail, including aging, environmental effects, and catastrophic events like accidents or earthquakes. For engineers and authorities, Structural Health Monitoring (SHM) has become an essential instrument in ensuring the longevity and safety of such infrastructure.

The process of continuously or occasionally inspecting structures to look for any indications of deterioration, abnormal behavior, or damage is known as structural health monitoring. It evaluates the structural integrity of civil engineering structures using a range of sensors and data analysis methods. The basic objective of SHM is to spot possible problems before they get serious so that repairs or maintenance can be done on time, improving safety and cutting expenses.

In this paper, we will be discussing structural health monitoring of bridges. With technological advancements, bridges around the world are becoming longer, larger, and there is a rapid increase in the number of old bridges. Bridges play a vital role in the transportation system and are designed to last for 50, 60, 70, or even more than 100 years. However, there are around 1.5 million bridges in the USA, Canada, and Europe that have completed their design life, which makes it essential to monitor their structural health and take urgent precautions in case of any adverse events. [1] [2] [3]

To better understand a structure's behavior, you need to be clear about why you want structured monitoring. Structural monitoring is briefly used to find out whether a structure or component is safe for daily use or not. Structural monitoring can also be used to understand what is the best way to protect a structure and extend its design life. Bridges naturally age like humans, but the implementation of a strategy based on monetary systems and their analysis to identify damage in real-time in the early stages is our goal. Instead of looking for disease, we should look for damages that may happen to a structure such as scarring cracks and corrosion. With the relatively high number of bridge collapses observed worldwide, structural health monitoring has gained significant importance. As an illustration, consider the Hintze Ribeiro Bridge in Portugal, the Morandi Bridge in Italy, and the I-35W Mississippi River Bridge in the USA [4]. Bridges are an important element of a country's transportation network, but they are prohibitively expensive to build and maintain. They are constantly exposed to the harmful effects of corrosion of reinforcing bars in concrete structures, increased traffic volume and overloading, or simply general deterioration and wear. Bridge health monitoring systems using IoT give us preliminary indications that we can easily save many lives and prevent losses.

2. RESEARCH AND FINDINGS

Studies on Structural Health Monitoring (SHM) date back several decades; The primary goal of the research under review is to monitor the deformation of bridges using a variety of sensors to assess their structural integrity. The data is then transmitted to a central location over a LoRaWAN network for analysis. The proposed systems were generally created using a

sensor unit consisting of an ultrasonic sensor, acceleration (vibration) sensor, IR sensor, fire sensor, and temperature sensor. All systems included IoT for long and short-range wireless data communication.

2.1 Internet of Things (IoT)

The Internet of Things, or IoT, is a network of interrelated devices that connect and exchange data with other IoT devices and the cloud. IoT devices are often equipped with technologies such as sensors and software and can include mechanical and digital machines as well as consumer objects [5]. With IoT, data can be transferred over a network without requiring human-to-human or human-to-computer interaction. The Internet of Things (IoT) ecosystem is made up of web-enabled smart devices that gather, transmit, and act upon data from their surroundings using embedded systems, including CPUs, sensors, and communication gear. IoT devices share the data they collect through sensors connecting to an IoT gateway, which acts as a central hub to which IoT devices can send data. In the studies we examined in this article, IoT-based systems, especially the LoRaWAN network were always used to monitor the structural health of bridges.

2.1.1 Characteristics of LoRaWAN Network

LoRa is an IoT wireless communication technology that operates in an unlicensed communication spectrum. A private network can serve as the base for a sensor network. According to LOS (Line of Sight), the signal reach distance is 5~10 km, and according to non-LOS, the wireless signal radius is 2~5 km [6].

What is the difference between Lora and LoRaWAN? Lora is a type of modulation. It's the method that is used for two entities to understand each other. Lora modulation uses chirp symbol and in addition to that the Lora frame format has been defined, which is mainly a preamble at the beginning to synchronize the receiver and then at the end a code for error detection. So, with Lora, the data can be transmitted from an end device to another end device, from an end device to a gateway, the other way round works as well, so from a gateway to an end device, and finally the Lora transmission between two gateways is also possible. The content of the frame which is called payload does not matter; anything can be put in it. The desired application protocol can be built depending on any unique use case.

However, it is important to use security features while sending data or information from an end device to a network server. Furthermore, a standard communication protocol is necessary to enable our end device to communicate with any network server. This process is called interoperability. Hence, we must define a protocol, a transmission method, this protocol is called '**LoRaWAN**'.

The LoRaWAN protocol involves a network server and an application server. Working with LoRaWAN limits transmission from one end device to a gateway; it does not allow transmission from one end device to another. The packet is subsequently sent to the network server by the gateway itself. A LoRa packet transmission conveying a message from the LoRaWAN protocol is occurring between the end device and the gateway. First of all, Lora is a must if we use LoRaWAN. However, it is feasible to work with Lora exclusively. For instance, we may send a Lora packet between two terminals without using an application

protocol. However, the LoRaWAN protocol is necessary if we wish to transmit data to the network server.

As with other secure networks, the LoRaWAN infrastructure requires data integrity, confidentiality, and authentication. It should be impossible for anyone to alter the transmitted frame. Whatever the end device transmits should be understood only by the intended receiver. Lastly, only authorized endpoints can submit data to the network server.

End-to-end security is intended to be supported by the LoRaWAN protocol. The ability of a network to encrypt data on the side of end devices and decrypt it on the user's end is known as end-to-end security. Therefore, in our scenario, the IoT platform itself ought to handle the LoRaWAN decryption. Furthermore, end-to-end security eliminates the possibility of malevolent incursions occurring between the user and the device.

In the Internet of Things universe, our first considerations when launching a fleet of devices are operators and subscriptions. However, LoRaWAN operates on open bands, making its frequencies universally accessible. This makes its systems unique. This frequency is 868 MHz in Europe, 915 MHz in the US, and 470 MHz in China.

LoRaWAN consists of four distinct networks: public operators network, private network, hybrid network, and community network. We need to consider the benefits and drawbacks of each of these architectures to determine which is the best fit for our use case.

We can install our own network servers and application servers, set up our own gateways, and even create our own IoT platform in a private network. The LoRaWAN operator provides us network coverage in public networks. Its numerous gateways are dispersed around the country and are all set up to transfer data to an operator network server. In the case of a public network, everything is owned by the operator aside from your own device because the server infrastructure is also provided. A significant disadvantage of a public network is that the gateway cannot be located anywhere. In that scenario, a hybrid network that combines the benefits of both public and private networks is an alternative that allows us to use our own gateways while utilizing the services of a LoRaWAN operator. As a result, we can control the network coverage, but the server will continue to be dependent on the LoRaWAN provider. In addition to my personal coverage, a community network offers network coverage. Consequently, not only can I profit from my gateway coverage but also from every gateway that is registered on this network server. Thus, the greater the number of users within the community, the greater the coverage available to all, and in certain cases, it's even free.

2.1.2 LoRaWAN network configuration and measurement equipment specifications

We require an operational network in order to manage a full LoRaWAN network configuration. Therefore, if you are running a private network, you need to have the LoRaWAN server configured yourself and have your gateway connected to the internet. And, if you decide to use a hybrid network architecture, you will need to have a subscription to a LoRaWAN provider and have your gateway up. Lastly, you can subscribe to a public network for a small fee if you only want to deploy your end device. Public network coverage is typically fairly strong, however you should confirm this on the website of the public operator.

In general, to get everything to function, we have four configuration steps. But, in the event that you select an alternative gateway for a public or community network, there will only be two configuration steps to go:

2.1.2.1 Gateway Configuration

Setting up the gateway is the first step, which enables it to recognize the protocol being used as well as the network server it is targeting. Regretfully, there isn't a single protocol specified by LoRaWAN between the network server and the gateway. So many people using LoRaWAN have created their own solution [7]. The packet forwarder, a small installed piece of software, manages the protocol used between the gateway and the network server. And it's quite simple to configure our packet forwarder after it's ready. Installing the best packet forwarder on the gateway is the next step after selecting it. Information to control this procedure is provided by all packet forwarder designers. We simply need to input the IP address of the network server together with the protocol's UDP or TCP port. Afterward, we will need to supply a private key and connection certificate if we have a secure transmission.

2.1.2.2 Gateway Registration

In essence, this task grants permission for this gateway to communicate with the server. Three pieces of information are required for registration: the gateway EUI, a name or ID, and occasionally both. The user selects these fields, which are merely there to aid the network server in categorizing our gateway. Lastly, we must define our region to use it in our frequency plan.

The Gateway EUI, a unique number that identifies the gateway and is supplied with the gateway upon purchase, is the most crucial piece of information among them. It can be modified occasionally, but for it to be distinct, the MAC address of the network interface linked to a random number is frequently used to generate it.

2.1.2.3 Device Registration

In the third step, we're going to register our device on the network server. Our network server will allow our device's LoRaWAN frame to reach the application server once it has registered. We can register hundreds of devices, each of which will have a unique configuration. Then we enter the LoRaWAN settings based on whether we want to utilize 'OTAA' or 'ABP' as the activation mode. On certain network servers, grouping devices together is possible. Designed to bring together devices with similar use cases, the groups—often referred to as applications—are formed. An application is simply a box or folder that we use to organize our devices.

2.1.2.3 Device Configuration

Finally, the fourth step is the device configuration. And, a new firmware is programmed onto the device itself to input the LoRaWAN settings.

2.2 List of Sensors

This section will look at sensors whose data is gathered over a LoRaWAN network. When it comes to wireless sensor networks, it is preferable for the sensors to have low power consumption, long battery life, affordable prices, and relatively tiny data sizes. The use of

such sensors for bridge monitoring has several benefits. First, the sensors are wireless, so no cables are needed to connect them to your data acquisition system. Secondly, the sensors are reasonably small, making installation simple. Lastly, they are reasonably priced, allowing for the installation of multiple sensors for the low cost.

2.2.1 RTD Sensors

RTDs use a platinum, nickel, or copper element whose resistance varies with temperature precisely and consistently. A temperature reading is then correlated with this resistance change. Longer cables or connectors, which by nature contribute more resistance to the circuit, can negatively affect the accuracy of an RTD when used; therefore, a means of compensating for this higher resistance must be found. This is the point at which various cabling configurations are useful. Different wiring configurations are available for RTDs, including two, three, and four wiring configurations overall [8]. The most precise findings are obtained using a four-wire RTD, which entirely isolates the resistance of the RTD element from the resistance of the wire. The four-wire bridge design measures temperature based on the voltage signal rather than resistance and fully adjusts for any resistance found in the cables or the connectors between them. Because of this, laboratories and other settings requiring great accuracy are the primary situations in which four-wire RTD systems are utilized [9].

2.2.2 Ultrasonic Sensors

Just like bats and dolphins use sonar to perceive their surroundings, ultrasonic sensors use sound waves at frequencies above the range of human hearing to determine distance. After sending out a high-frequency pulse into the atmosphere, the sensor waits for an object to reflect the identical signal back to it [10]. The time difference between sending and receiving is multiplied by the sound speed and divided by two to determine the distance from the sensor to that object.

$$distance = \frac{time \times sound\ speed}{2}$$

2.2.3 Acceleration Sensors

Vibration sensor is another name for an accelerometer. In essence, they detect the degree of acceleration, and based on their measuring range, they can then communicate this acceleration value to other systems that are connected. Vibration sensors can also be employed as safety barriers to safeguard systems and facilities in the event of a potential earthquake and to monitor seismic activity [11].

2.2.4 Load Cell

Load Cell, is a transducer that produces a measurable electrical output signal from an input force, mechanical load, weight, tension, compression, or pressure.

2.2.5 Temperature and Humidity Sensors

Temperature and humidity sensor, These are inexpensive electronic devices with humidity and air temperature sensors. They can also report the temperature and humidity data by converting it into electrical impulses. They include an 8-bit microprocessor to output the

temperature and humidity values as serial data, as well as a specialized NTC for measuring temperature [12].

2.2.6 IR Sensor

An infrared sensor is a gadget that can identify infrared radiation in its surroundings, even when it's invisible to the human eye, and it can also generate an electrical signal when it does so. An infrared sensor can measure an object's temperature and detect motion [13].

2.2.7 Strain Gauge

A sensor known as a strain gauge is one whose strain varies in response to variations in the voltage of electrical resistance that is being measured [14]. Strain is the material's displacement or distortion brought on by an applied stress.

2.2.8 Flexible Flex Sensors

Flex sensors are used to detect structural bends [15]. The quantity of flaws that will cause a sensor to bend in the wrong direction is measured by a flex sensor. The multitude of sensors makes it simple to identify any kinks that may be present.

3. DISCUSSIONS

The use of less expensive MEMS sensors in favor of pricey piezoelectric ones is a significant development in SHM. A comparison of a MEMS sensor and a piezoelectric sensor for vibration-based SHM is given in [16], showing that MEMS is a practical technology for SHM with notable cost savings. Another example is provided by [17], which is the primary reference used in this study and has been verified in production. The primary drawbacks of this design are as follows: (i) it requires power cabling and relies on short-range, power-hungry wireless communication (Wi-Fi) for data; (ii) it is not intended for battery operation.

In [18], They examined and adjusted the primary parameters of the NB-IoT communication protocol, which was selected due to its low power consumption and ability to offer wireless connectivity to the 4G (and soon to be 5G) global infrastructure network—making it appropriate for ongoing monitoring. They compared the newest NB-IoT modules available and determined which would work best in a continuous SHM situation. They demonstrated the hardware and software architecture of a SHM node that can run independently for up to ten years, or even forever with the help of a tiny 72 cm^2 solar panel. By contrasting their inexpensive instruments with a cutting-edge piezoelectric transducer utilized in upscale commercial instrumentation for transient cabled installations, they verified the system's measurement accuracy. The accuracy of estimating the modal vibration frequencies differs by less than 0.08%, according to the results, and there is a cost savings of about 10×. Furthermore, because of the long operation lifetime and complete lack of connections, their approach makes deployment simple. Finally, they demonstrate three laboratory studies on structural damage that validate the applicability of their method in SHM settings.

The system suggested by [19] was put to the test using particular stress assessment in order to verify the crack meters performance in demanding conditions. The ceramic material that

serves as the reference substrate and has an extremely low thermal expansion coefficient of $0.37\mu\text{m}/^\circ\text{C}$ is glued to the plastic support. A thermal chamber with realistic weather conditions was used to test every component, including the batteries and electronics. The initial experiments were conducted between -15 and 65°C , which are large temperature variable ranges, in order to confirm the hysteresis inaccuracy. Unpredictable developments make it challenging to make up for these kinds of problems. The primary causes of hysteresis are (1) Allegro A1319; (2) Non-reversible changes in the magnetic field; and (3) Non-reversible PLA box thermal expansion. In the initial test, a ceramic support was directly fixed with magnets and a Hall sensor (no plastic box or support). Verifying the hysteresis component resulting from the non-reversible fluctuation of the magnetic field was the aim. The sensor behaves very well ($\pm 5\mu\text{m}$) in the temperature range of -15 to 65°C ; in the range of 7 to 45°C , the hysteresis component is almost nonexistent ($\pm 2\mu\text{m}$). They then assessed the ABS case's crack meter's overall components. The results in this instance indicate a notable hysteresis, which impairs measurement accuracy. The inaccuracy in the ($-10 - 65^\circ\text{C}$) range is $\pm 20\mu\text{m}$. The crack meter features are ensured and the hysteresis error is contained at $\pm 5\mu\text{m}$ within the temperature range of 7 to 45°C . The ABS support prevents the crack meter from reaching its maximum sensitivity, but it does enable the creation of a relatively affordable tool. The polycarbonate support was used to acquire the results. Verifying the hysteresis component resulting from non-reversible polycarbonate change was the aim. The sensor's behavior is better in the temperature range of -15 to 65°C when compared to ABS support. The hysteresis is decreased from $\pm 20\mu\text{m}$ to $\pm 5\mu\text{m}$ and then to only $\pm 3\mu\text{m}$ in the 7 to 45°C region. When the temperature's first derivative varies, an odd effect appears. Tiny spikes impact the measurement of distance, causing a nonlinear inaccuracy of about $5\mu\text{m}$. However, the effect can be seen as minimal because of the little window of time in which it reveals itself. The long-term output response of the crack meter was displayed with a resolution of $\pm 1\mu\text{m}$ following the implementation of linear temperature adjustment.

In [20] LoRa P2P system was proposed, and the suggested LoRa P2P communication sequence's security was examined against the five assaults. Which are, Tracking attack, Man-In-The-Middle attack, Replay attack, Key Disclosure attack and DE-Synchronization attack. They unveiled the TenSense M30, an innovative Internet of Things sensor node designed for smart city integration that monitors pre-tension in bolted joints. The suggested design, in contrast to the products already on the market, enables remote, accurate monitoring of the pre-tension load on bolted joints without requiring any changes to the target structure or the bolt itself. The TenSense M30 node's physical examination and FEA analysis both demonstrated that the design is safe under the imposed pre-tension force. Additionally, it was evident from the physical testing that the system can accurately track the relevant strain. Through LoRa P2P, the suggested communication protocol guarantees a secure channel. In the worst case scenario, battery life is anticipated to be more than five years when using the 20 dBm transmission mode. The current coverage range, in a non-line-of-sight scenario, reaches over 800 meters. All of this guarantees that the design can monitor the target construction's health on a daily basis.

A proof of concept for a LoRaWAN battery-free wireless sensing node for SHM applications in the construction industry is provided by the sensing node prototype that was developed and presented in [21]. It has been suggested to implement a wireless sensor network as part of a cyber-physical system for structural health monitoring applications in the construction industry. It is made up of a wireless mesh network with LoRaWAN sensing and communication nodes that don't require batteries. Two sensing nodes and one communication node made up a basic implementation that was experimentally tested over the air and presented (for proof-of-concept purposes). Two battery-free sensing nodes that are powered wirelessly by a single dedicated RF power source measure the temperature and relative humidity. Using a cold-start process, the sensing nodes are turned on and begin to function as long as they are exposed to electromagnetic waves with a power density greater than $0.5 \mu\text{W}/\text{cm}^2$. The experimental results show that the temperature and relative humidity data that the sensing nodes have acquired may be wirelessly sent to a communicative node, such as a LoRa gateway that is 1.3 km away from the sensing node, utilizing LoRa technology and the LoRaWAN protocol. By connecting their streamlined sensor network to the Internet, this communication node creates a link between the real and virtual worlds. The energy autonomy of the sensing nodes is achieved by the use of a wireless power transmission mechanism, which allows periodicity of measurement and data transmission to be controlled without requiring any hardware or software modifications to the sensing nodes. The employment of a wireless power transmission system, which can be adjusted to control the periodicity of the measurement and communication, ensures energy autonomy. This SN prototype can be enhanced to be more comprehensive, effective, small, and pertinent for the intended applications, as it is neither integrated nor downsized. Thus, they have put up a comprehensive plan for the wireless, long-distance communication of sensor nodes via far-field radio frequency power transmission, which eliminates the need for batteries and makes use of LoRa technology and the LoRaWAN protocol. The power transmission system of the sensing nodes regulates the temperature and relative humidity that they measure. With the eventual goal of being implemented within reinforced precast concrete, this prototype is presently working toward cyber-physical systems designed for structural health monitoring applications in the construction arena.

Another study on the use of a LoRa LPWAN-based wireless measurement system for monitoring the structural health of bridges was carried out in [6]. Additionally, a self-networked LoRa LPWAN-based sensor network was built and implemented on the cable-stayed bridge portion of the Cheonsa Bridge, which is situated in Shinan-gun, Jeollanam-do. The gateway for receiving wireless signals in the LoRa LPWAN sensor network is a smart sensor node with integrated MEMS accelerometers at one on the outside and one inside the reinforced type, ten cables on the cable-stayed bridge, two on the pylons, and four inside the reinforced type. It is made up of external measuring tools that are attached to the device, such as a member thermometer and an elastic displacement gauge. Through the use of a built-in MEMS accelerometer, the self-developed distributed processing-based smart sensor node determines and wirelessly transmits the cable tension, pylon slope, and reinforced natural

frequency. It also transmits the measurement results of the stretchable displacement gauge and member thermometer that are connected via an external interface. Smart sensor nodes gather it and send it to the LoRa network server. The sensor network used to monitor the structural health of the newly built bridge is based on LoRa LPWAN. Accuracy is determined by comparing the sensor network's robustness with that of existing wired-based sensor networks and by analyzing wireless signal characteristics like reception rate. It was investigated whether the wireless measurement system might be used on big bridges. A bridge structural health monitoring system can be inexpensively built, run, and maintained by utilizing a LoRa LPWAN-based sensor network. The current wire-based measuring and maintenance systems are economical to install, operate, and maintain, despite the fact that bridges are decaying at a rapid rate.

4. CONCLUSION

Wireless sensor technology has advanced quickly in the past several years and found use in many different fields. In the context of structural monitoring, wireless communications combined with conventional structural sensors can significantly lower the cost of monitoring systems and offer features not seen in currently available commercial structural monitoring platforms. For the sake of public safety, monitoring systems for bridge structural health are therefore necessary. The primary goal is to use a sensor network to identify bridge degradation and to transmit the information that was collected from the sensors through a private LoRaWAN network. LoRaWAN, one low-power wide area network (LPWAN) technology that has attracted a lot of interest from the research community recently. It provides communication over a large covered area with low power and low data rate. Bridge health monitoring problems can be resolved with the help of sensors and the internet of things. Numerous lives can be saved by these technologies. This work can be expanded by creating a sophisticated system with industry-grade sensors and controllers, adapting it to practical uses, and providing in-depth dynamic signal analysis for the interpretation of other crucial factors.

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